

Understanding Beal Conjecture extending Goldbach

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Abstract

Beal conjecture can be proved extending the understanding of Goldbach's discussion.

1 Beal Conjecture

Beal conjecture is stated as following[Beal(1997)]:

If $A^x + B^y = C^z$ where "A", "B", "C", "x", "y", "z" are positive integers and "x", "y", "z" are ≥ 3 , do "A", "B", and "C" have a common prime factor?

This conjecture can be proved to be true by extending the understanding of Goldbach[Yoon(2023)].

2 Extending Goldbach

Goldbach's discussion is stated as following and can be understood as proven true[Yoon(2024)]:

Theorem 2.1 Any integer number larger than zero can be expressed in orderly combination of two conditions for C and prime number p, p' :

$$\exists C \begin{cases} C \nmid 2 \implies 1 + p + p' \\ C \mid 2 \implies p + p' \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Assuming that C is C , then summation of Beal conjecture can be represented as following:

$$\exists A, B, C, x, y, z \begin{cases} C \nmid 2 \implies A^x + B^y = (p + p' + 1)^z \\ C \mid 2 \implies A^x + B^y = (p + p')^z \end{cases}$$

By extending so, A and B can be also interpreted repeatedly same. Assuming that $p, q, r, p', q', r' \in \mathbb{P}$:

$$\exists A, B, C, x, y, z \begin{cases} A \nmid 2 \implies \begin{cases} B \nmid 2 \implies \begin{cases} C \nmid 2 \implies \text{Case 1. } (q + q' + 1)^x + (r + r' + 1)^y = (p + p' + 1)^z \\ C \mid 2 \implies \text{Case 2. } (q + q' + 1)^x + (r + r' + 1)^y = (p + p')^z \end{cases} \\ B \mid 2 \implies \begin{cases} C \nmid 2 \implies \text{Case 3. } (q + q' + 1)^x + (r + r')^y = (p + p' + 1)^z \\ C \mid 2 \implies \text{Case 4. } (q + q' + 1)^x + (r + r')^y = (p + p')^z \end{cases} \end{cases} \\ A \mid 2 \implies \begin{cases} B \nmid 2 \implies \begin{cases} C \nmid 2 \implies \text{Case 5. } (q + q')^x + (r + r' + 1)^y = (p + p' + 1)^z \\ C \mid 2 \implies \text{Case 6. } (q + q')^x + (r + r' + 1)^y = (p + p')^z \end{cases} \\ B \mid 2 \implies \begin{cases} C \nmid 2 \implies \text{Case 7. } (q + q')^x + (r + r')^y = (p + p' + 1)^z \\ C \mid 2 \implies \text{Case 8. } (q + q')^x + (r + r')^y = (p + p')^z \end{cases} \end{cases} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

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3 Understanding Cases of Beal Conjecture

The problem is, when any $A^x + B^y = C^z$ constitutes disparity between even and odd number. Assuming that $p, p', p'', p''', q, q', q'', q''', r, r', r'', r''' \in \mathbb{P}$

3.1 Case 1

Case 1 is contradictory to statement of Beal conjecture. Any sum of two odd number cannot be odd number.

3.2 Case 2

In case 2, any sum of two odd number constitutes even number. Then:

$$\begin{aligned}(q + q' + 1)^x + (r + r' + 1)^y &= 2^z(p'' + p''' + 1)^z \\ \implies (2^m(q'' + q''' + 1) + 1)^x + (2^n(r'' + r''' + 1) + 1)^y &= 2^z(p'' + p''' + 1)^z \\ \implies A := 2^m A' + 1, B := 2^n B' + 1 \implies (2^m A' + 1)^x + (2^n B' + 1)^y &= 2^z(C')^z \\ \implies \exists A'', B'' \implies 2^{m \cdot x} A'' + 2^{n \cdot y} B'' + 2 &= 2^z(C')^z\end{aligned}$$

And common divisor comes out.

3.3 Case 3

In case 3, any sum of odd and even number constitutes odd number.

$$\begin{aligned}(q + q' + 1)^x + 2^y(r'' + r''' + 1)^y &= (p + p' + 1)^z \\ \implies (q + q' + 1)^x - (p + p' + 1)^z &= 2^y(r'' + r''' + 1)^y = 2^y(C')^y \\ \implies 2^x(q'' + q''' + 1)^x - 2^z(p'' + p''' + 1)^z &= 2^y(r'' + r''' + 1)^y \\ = 2^x(A')^x - 2^z(C')^z = 2^y(B')^y, \exists A' := 2^x A, B' := 2^y B, C' := 2^z C\end{aligned}$$

And common divisor comes out.

3.4 Case 4

Case 4 is contradictory to statement of Beal conjecture. Any sum of odd and even number cannot be even number.

3.5 Case 5

Case 5 follows a case of case 3.

3.6 Case 6

Case 6 is contradictory to statement of Beal conjecture. Any sum of even and odd number cannot be even number.

3.7 Case 7

Case 7 is contradictory to statement of Beal conjecture. Any sum of even numbers cannot be odd number.

3.8 Case 8

Case 8 shows the statement true in Beal conjecture such that any sum of two even number is even number and can be dividable by number 2.

References

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